

Influence of slaked lime on hydration kinetics of Portland cement

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ABSTRACT

Due to the lower calcification temperature and better carbon sequestration performance, calcium lime binders are accepted as sustainable alternatives to conventional Portland cement in masonry structures. However, calcium lime binders mainly get hardened through long-term carbonation, and the strength development is slow. To overcome this drawback and ensure the mechanical performance at early ages, mixtures of slaked lime (i.e., Ca(OH)₂) and Portland cement are preferred in engineering practice. To investigate the hydration kinetics of lime-cement binders, especially to clarify the influence of lime-to-cement ratio (*l/c* ratio), calorimetry tests, X-ray diffraction (XRD) and thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were carried out on binders with four different lime-to-cement ratios (*l/c*=0.0, 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0). Compared to pure cement paste, earlier occurrence of the main hydration peak (i.e., formation of C-S-H) and shorter induction period were observed in lime-cement binders, suggesting that the hydration is facilitated by additional slaked lime. The acceleration effect was further proved by quantitative analyses of XRD results and TGA, as the consumption rates of all four major phases (i.e., C₃S, C₂S, C₃A and C₄AF) increased with *l/c* ratio, and quicker transformation from Ettringite to AFm phases were observed in lime-cement binders. Further comparisons with inert SiO₂ fillers suggest that the acceleration effect is attributed to both physical and chemical influences, and detailed influence mechanisms will be investigated in future research.

KEYWORDS: *Slaked lime, Portland cement, hydration kinetics*

1. Introduction

Compared to Portland cement, calcium lime is calcined at lower temperatures, and the material itself could absorb CO₂ during the hardening process. Therefore, it is believed to be an ideal alternative to conventional cementitious materials in applications like plastering materials and joint materials between masonry blocks (Alvarez et al. 2021). However, one significant drawback of calcium lime binders is the poor early-age mechanical performance. Instead of gaining strength through hydration, calcium lime binders get hardened through carbonation, which may take months or even years. Therefore, in engineering practice, the mixture of calcium lime and conventional Portland cement is preferred to keep the balance between sustainability and mechanical properties (Gulbe et al. 2017).

Several previous studies have investigated the hydration process of lime-cement binders. For example, Cizer (2009) observed that the induction period could be greatly shortened by additional slaked lime. Fourmentin et al. (2015) observed similar results in their tests. However, neither of these investigations discussed the influence during the whole hydration process, and the detailed influence of slaked lime on cement hydration is still unclear.

Therefore, in this research, hydration process of four different lime-cement binders were investigated through the combined use of thermogravimetric analyses (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and

calorimetry. Based on these test results, hydration kinetics of lime-cement binders, as well as related influence mechanisms, will be discussed.

2. Materials and Methods

CEM I 42.5N cement from ENCI and CL-90S slaked lime from Lhoist were used in this research. Properties of these raw materials are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Raw material properties

Categories	Properties (Units)	Cement	Lime	Methods
Physical properties	Density (g/cm ³)	3.15	2.30	Pycnometer
	Specific surface area (m ² /g)	0.86	13.46	Nitrogen sorption (BET)
	Mean particle size D_{43} (μm)	29.41	15.56	Laser diffraction
Chemical composition	Alite C ₃ S (%)	62.90	N/A	XRD
	Belite C ₂ S (%)	10.26	N/A	XRD
	Alumina C ₃ A (%)	5.70	N/A	XRD
	Ferrite C ₄ AF (%)	10.37	N/A	XRD
	Portlandite CH (%)	N/A	96.30	XRD/TG
	Calcite CĈ (%)	N/A	3.70	XRD/TG
	Sulfates (%)	5.95	N/A	XRD

In order to investigate the influence of l/c ratio, three groups of lime-cement binders were considered in this research, and one group of pure cement paste was prepared for comparisons. Detailed mixture designs are presented in Table 2. It should be noted that, due to the large specific surface area of lime, a higher w/b ratio (0.8) was designed for all lime-cement binders to keep the consistency at a similar level.

Table 2 Mixture designs

Groups	Lime-to-cement (l/c) ratio	Water-to-binder (w/b) ratio
C100L0	0.0	0.6
C67L33	0.5	0.8
C50L50	1.0	
C33L67	2.0	

Following procedures recommended by Snellings et al. (2018), powder samples were collected after 6 hours, 1 day, 3 days, 7 days and 14 days for TGA and XRD. In the former test, around 30mg sample was heated to 1200°C at a rate of 10K/min. In the latter analysis, 10% silicon powder was added as the internal standard, and the sample was scanned from 5° 2θ to 75° 2θ, with a stepwise of 0.02° 2θ.

Meanwhile, hydration heat release during the first 7 days (at 20°C) were measured through isothermal calorimetry. For comparisons, inert SiO₂ fillers with a similar specific surface area (11.94m²/g) were also used to reflect the filler effect. All test results will be presented and discussed in the following section.

3. Results and Discussions

Figure 1 Representative DTG curves of hydration products

As shown in Figure 1, with the increase of lime content, the dehydration peak of Ca(OH)₂ at around 480°C becomes more significant. Meanwhile, due to the inevitable existence of CaCO₃ in slaked lime (shown in Table 1), as well as carbonation during the mixing and sample preparation process, decarbonation peaks at around 700°C were observed in lime-cement binders. However, after several days, these peaks become less obvious, indicating that CaCO₃ was consumed during the hydration process. As a result, calcium carboaluminate hydrate (C-A-Ĉ-H) was found in XRD tests (shown in Figure 2).

Regarding dehydration of other products, two peaks were observed between 50°C and 300°C. The peak at around 100°C appears right within the first day. This is mainly attributed to the rapid formation of ettringite and C-S-H. With the development of hydration, AFm phases are formed through continuous reactions between ettringite and cement clinkers. Therefore, the first peak gradually gets lower, and a new peak at around 170°C grows with time. Other AFm phases, like C-A-Ĉ-H, should also contribute to the second peak, but their contributions should be marginal, as there is no obvious peak detected after 200°C. After 14 days, the second peak become dominant in lime-cement binders, while the first peak is still more obvious in pure cement paste. Therefore, it can be concluded that the additional slaked lime could facilitate the formation of AFm.

Figure 2 Typical XRD patterns of hydration products

Such acceleration effect could be better reflected through quantitative analyses of tests mentioned above. By calculating mass losses between 50°C and 300°C, and normalizing them with cement proportion, it is obvious that the normalized mass loss increases with the lime content. Even though the mass loss cannot be clearly attributed to the dehydration of one single phase, this indicator can still prove that the total amount of hydration products is greater in groups with more slaked lime inside (shown in Figure 3a).

(a) Normalized mass losses observed in TGA

(b) Hydration degrees of four major phases after 14 days

Figure 3 Quantitative analyses of TGA and XRD results

Through Rietveld refinements of XRD results, hydration degrees of four major hydraulic phases (i.e., C_3S , C_2S , C_3A , C_4AF) could be assessed (shown in Figure 3b). Despite the semi-quantitative nature of the analysis method, the accelerated hydration of all four phases is still obvious. However, the acceleration effect seems less relevant to the lime content, but vary significantly among different phases. For C_3S , C_3A and C_4AF , hydration degrees were increased by 8%-12%, while for C_2S , the increment is less obvious. A possible explanation to these phenomena is that the rapid hydration in early ages. Due to the growth of hydration products, further hydration reactions, especially the hydration of C_2S , could be greatly hindered, so the influence of slaked lime becomes less significant.

Several possible explanations to the acceleration effect have been proposed in previous investigations (e.g., Cizer 2009, Fourmentin et al. 2015), and among them the most reasonable one is the filler effect.

Due to the limited solubility of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, most of the slaked lime will not dissolve during the mixing process, and therefore could provide additional precipitation surface for hydration products. However, through comparisons with inert SiO_2 fillers (shown in Figure 4), it is clear that the induction period is significantly shorter in lime-cement binders, and the peak heat flow is also greater. Given that the surface area of inert SiO_2 fillers is similar to that of slaked lime particles, the decrease in the induction period should be more likely attributed to chemical effects, like higher affinity to hydration products and higher calcium concentration in pore solution systems. The detailed influence mechanism will be further investigated through ICP-OES tests and microscopy observations.

Figure 4 Heat release during the hydration process

4. Conclusions

In this research, hydration process of four typical lime-cement binders has been investigated, and related influence mechanisms have been briefly discussed. Within the scope of this research, the following conclusions could be drawn:

- (1) The additional slaked lime could facilitate the formation of ettringite and C-S-H, as well as the formation of AFm.
- (2) Hydration of all four hydraulic phases could be accelerated by slaked lime, but the acceleration effect is less significant on C_2S . This phenomenon may be related to the rapid formation of hydration products.
- (3) The acceleration effect should be not only attributed to physical filler effect, but also related to chemical effects, which will be investigated in future research.

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